

**Supplementary materials for the paper: “Putting
Robots in Context: Challenging the Influence of Voice
and Empathic Behaviour on Trust” presented at IEEE
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Scripts of the utterances spoken by Pepper to express affective and cognitive empathy in the 3 extracts used in the first online study (OS1) and in the corn maze navigation video of the second online study (OS2)

Video	Affective Empathy	Cognitive Empathy
Fencing - OS1	<p>Fencing is an organized sport involving the use of a sword for attack and defense according to set movements and rules. Although the use of swords dates to prehistoric times and swordplay to ancient civilizations, the organized sport of fencing began only at the end of the 19th century. The history of fencing is fascinating, I did not know that the sport as we know it today was this young! The Romans brought sword combat to a highly systematic art that was taught to both their legions and their gladiators. Gladiators were trained in schools by professional instructors. Beginners practiced with a wooden sword called a rudis. More-advanced training took place with heavier weapons than those used in actual combat. I feel bad for all those gladiators and slaves that were forced to risk their lives for the amusement of rich people.</p>	<p>Fencing is an organized sport involving the use of a sword for attack and defense according to set movements and rules. Although the use of swords dates to prehistoric times and swordplay to ancient civilizations, the organized sport of fencing began only at the end of the 19th century. I bet you did not know that fencing as we see it today is such a young sport. The Romans brought sword combat to a highly systematic art that was taught to both their legions and their gladiators. Gladiators were trained in schools by professional instructors. Beginners practiced with a wooden sword called a rudis. More-advanced training took place with heavier weapons than those used in actual combat. I also think that, if Romans were to use their gladiators as part of their legions, they would have had an even more powerful army!</p>

<p>Pluto - OS1</p>	<p>Pluto, large, distant member of the solar system that formerly was regarded as the outermost and smallest planet. It also was considered the most recently discovered planet, having been found in 1930. In August 2006 the International Astronomical Union voted to remove Pluto from the list of planets and give it the new classification of dwarf planet. Poor Pluto, isn't it a bit unfair to get demoted like that out of the blue? It will always be a planet to me. The change reflects astronomers' realization that Pluto is a large member of the Kuiper belt, a collection of debris of ice and rock left over from the formation of the solar system and now revolving around the Sun beyond Neptune's orbit. Being an astronaut has always been a dream of mine. It would be awesome to be able to witness these astronomical phenomena.</p>	<p>Pluto, large, distant member of the solar system that formerly was regarded as the outermost and smallest planet. It also was considered the most recently discovered planet, having been found in 1930. In August 2006 the International Astronomical Union voted to remove Pluto from the list of planets and give it the new classification of dwarf planet. I think you might have already known this about Pluto. We can both agree that his life as a planet has been short. The change reflects astronomers' realization that Pluto is a large member of the Kuiper belt, a collection of debris of ice and rock left over from the formation of the solar system and now revolving around the Sun beyond Neptune's orbit. I can see why the astronomical union decided to demote Pluto to dwarf planet, it is just a bigger piece of debris.</p>
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Pangolins - OS1	<p>Pangolin, also called scaly anteater, is any of about eight species of armoured placental mammals of the order Pholidota. The name pangolin, from the Malay meaning “rolling over,” refers to this animal’s habit of curling into a ball when threatened. Pangolins are found in tropical Asia and Africa. Pangolins are so adorable, curling into a ball when threatened is such a cute thing to do! Pangolins feed mainly on termites but also eat ants and other insects. They locate prey by smell and use their forefeet to rip open nests. Young pangolins are soft-scaled at birth and are carried on the female’s back for some time. Life span in the wild is unknown; however, some captive animals have lived as long as 20 years. They also seem pretty amazing, their sense of smell is so advanced! I am happy they are able to live that long.</p>	<p>Pangolin, also called scaly anteater, is any of about eight species of armoured placental mammals of the order Pholidota. The name pangolin, from the Malay meaning “rolling over,” refers to this animal’s habit of curling into a ball when threatened. Pangolins are found in tropical Asia and Africa. I believe we can both agree that their strategy to stay safe is not an effective one, even armoured! Pangolins feed mainly on termites but also eat ants and other insects. They locate prey by smell and use their forefeet to rip open nests. Young pangolins are soft-scaled at birth and are carried on the female’s back for some time. Life span in the wild is unknown; however, some captive animals have lived as long as 20 years. know what you are thinking: if only our pets could live this long, right?</p>
Corn Maze - OS2	<p>Here, we should turn right. Don’t worry if you think turning right is scary. I am with you on this one!</p>	<p>Here, we should turn right. I understand you might want to take the safest option and not risk getting lost any further.</p>

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